

FIN STRUCTURES OF THE AIRBUS FAMILY EXPERIENCE WITH ADVANCED COMPOSITES

Dieter Schulz
Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm GmbH
Civil Aircraft Division

1. ABSTRACT

MBB has developed rudder and fin box structures in carbon fibre composites for the AIRBUS wide and narrow body versions. In-service experience has been gained since 1981. Applied design features and dimensioning principles are described. Qualification of the chosen designs and the selected materials with respect to static and fatigue strength, damage tolerance and maintenance requirements is explained. Summarizing remarks are made on the applied manufacturing and quality assurance principles reflecting to the gathered experience up to now.

Fig. 1 AIRBUS WIDE AND NARROW BODY VERTICAL TAILS

2. INTRODUCTION

Up to Dec. 1988 more than 250 composite rudders and 150 composite fin boxes have been employed on Airbus aircraft, flying with different airlines all over the world. The leading rudder has accumulated approx. 18000 flight hours and the leading fin box approx. 7000 flight hours (Fig. 2).

	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89
Rudder Wide Body	▼ Launch of Development ▼ 1. Flight Airline Experimental ▼ Airline Operation												
Fin Box Wide Body	▼ Launch of Research Program ▼ Launch of Development ▼ Airline Operation												
Rudder and Fin Box Narrow Body	▼ Launch of Development ▼ Airline Operation												

FIG. 2 AIRBUS FIN STRUCTURES - APPLICATION OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES

Many reports [1]-[9] have been published concerning the design, calculation, manufacturing, testing and certification approach of the wide and narrow body fin structures. The aim of this paper is to present the summary of the experiences gained during the last 10 years of these structures. The main reason for making use of advanced light weight composites in aircraft structures, was initiated by economical considerations.

FIG. 3 COMPOSITION OF THE DIRECT OPERATING COSTS FOR THE AIRBUS A340

3. FLIGHT EVALUATION

In 1976 a decision was made within MBB to go-ahead with the investment necessary for the application of advanced composites to the Airbus structures. At that time the broad applica-

tion of advanced composites into commercial airline service even of secondary structures, was not conceivable. Industries, airlines and authorities needed experience with single parts flying on in-service aircraft. Deutsche Lufthansa and MBB started an experimental program for spoilers, floor struts, leading edges and a rudder. The results from this program in general were positive, only some local findings were observed on the spoilers and the rudder resulting from poor sealing, vibration and incompatible material combinations. Data was gained about the behaviour of the new materials under in-service environmental conditions. In 1983 advanced composites were applied to all above mentioned parts on the A310 series aircraft.

4. PREPARATION OF SERVICE APPLICATION BY RESEARCH PROGRAMS

In 1978 a research program, sponsored by the German Government was initiated to investigate all critical subjects, which could render the introduction of modern composites into primary aircraft structures. For this purpose the Airbus A300/A310 fin box was selected to be designed with Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP). The main objectives of the research program were:

- reduction of the structural weight by approximately 20%
- to realize comparable production cost with respect to the existing metal fin box
- acceptable maintenance costs

All targets should be achieved without any degradation in safety.

The research program was started with a team of engineers having experience in the development of the A300 metal fin box, completed by an engineering staff with special experience on composites. The team work covered all significant development areas such as design, structural mechanics, materials, testing, design to cost, tooling, manufacturing and maintenance. All research work aimed to reach as quick as possible a status which could allow the transfer of the research program into an industrial program. In 1982 sufficient positive results had been gained to enable and encourage MBB and Airbus Industrie management to decide that the A310-300 series should be equipped with a composite fin box. At the end of 1985 Swiss Air was the first airline flying with an all composite vertical stabilizer on the A310-300 series.

FIG. 4 CROSS SECTION OF A310 AND A320 VERTICAL TAIL

5. DESIGN OF THE RUDDER

FIG. 5 AIRBUS RUDDER

The rudders of the wide and narrow bodied Airbus models are very similar in structural design. In principle these rudders consist only of a spar, two sandwich side panels and an upper and lower end rib (Fig.5). No inner ribs are available. The comparison of the A300/A310 metal and composite rudders (Fig. 6) make obvious that the number of parts were reduced significantly, leading to lower labour costs. As shown in Fig. 7 large areas of the side panels consist of a light Nomex core covered by two layers of glass and carbon fibre fabric resulting in a specific panel weight of 2.0 kg/m². This specific weight is comparable with the realized weight of the multi-rib composite rudders of the wide body aircraft DC10 (2.0 kg/m²) [10]. A comparison of the total composite rudder weight referred to the rudder areas comprises as follows:

$$\text{A310 : } 175.0 \text{ kg}/16.1 \text{ m}^2 = 10.9 \text{ kg/m}^2$$

$$\text{DC10 : } 27.85 \text{ kg}/2.16 \text{ m}^2 = 12.9 \text{ kg/m}^2$$

FIG. 6 COMPARISON OF THE METAL AND CFC RUDDERS

FIG. 7 CFC RUDDER STRUCTURAL DESIGN

The Airbus rudder shows that the sandwich design can be competitive in comparison to the multirib design, also with respect to weight saving. Using the sandwich design MBB realized a weight saving of 18% for the wide body rudder.

The main differences of the wide and narrow body rudders are presented in Fig. 4 .

While the spar of the wide body rudder is a sandwich one, a solid laminate construction was applied to the A320 rudder. When replacing the wide body metal rudder, the time schedule was so tight that the existing metal fittings had to be used. For the new A320 rudder the fit-

tings were designed as CFRP parts. This led however to more expensive parts, but especially for fittings a considerable weight saving percentage was possible as demonstrated in Fig. 8.

FIG. 8 WEIGHT COMPARISON

6. DESIGN OF THE FIN BOXES

FIG. 9 STIFFENERS OF THE PANELS

As shown in Fig. 4 the fin boxes were designed as monolithic structures made of laminated parts with integrated stiffeners having a pitch of 100 mm for the A310 and 115 mm for the A320. The main parts of the fin boxes are the skin panels, spars, ribs and fittings. Most of the integral parts are made from fabric materials, the use of tapes is limited to local stiffening purposes at stringers and spar caps. The panels contain the skin laminates, the skin stiffeners which are I-stringers and rib cleats, the spar caps and three fuselage attachment fittings. The typical construction is demonstrated in Fig. 9. The stringer webs with inner and outer flanges as well as the spar caps are laid up from +/- 45° fabric prepregs and draped

around the aluminium module cores. All modules are joined together in an assembly rig and the reinforcing tapes are laid up at the top and bottom of the stringers so as to give sufficient stiffness. All these parts are subassembled in a noncured stage. The precured inner and outer halves of each main fuselage fitting are assembled with the skin laminates and the modules and are cured in a single autoclave process. The spar webs are designed as flat blade stiffened laminates with beaded maintenance holes. Fittings for the transmission of shear loads to the fuselage are integral. The applied manufacturing techniques are the same as used for the skin panels. 9 web type and 9 framework ribs support the wide body panels and 11 web type ribs are used to support the narrow body panels. The web type ribs of the A310 and A320 were designed following the same design principles as applied to the spars that means flat blade stiffened laminates. Referring to the rudder hinge arms and rudder supporting fittings a broader application of composites was applied to the more recent design of the A320 (Fig. 4). In the assembly line all single parts are joined together using titanium bolts and Hi-lock rivets. Those areas where CFRP material meets directly metallic parts, the CFRP surface was covered with glass fibre layers in order to prevent electrolytical corrosion

of the metal parts. The CFRP fin is protected against lightning strike damages by a system of aluminium stripes at the leading, trailing and upper edges of the CFRP structures. Connection between the lightning strike protection system of the rudder, the fin box and the metallic fuselage were designed on the basis of extensive analysis and testing. No metal mesh was found to be necessary to protect the global surfaces of the composite parts. In total a weight saving of 23% could be realized for the wide body fin box.

7. MATERIALS AND FABRICATION

The same carbon fibre-resin materials were used for the rudder and fin box structures. For all parts T300 fibres in combination with the 125°C curing HEXCEL F550 and CIBA Fibredux 913C were qualified. In order to provide an adequate design data base, the environmental effects on the design properties of the material system had to be investigated.

For production of composite CFRP fin box and rudder assemblies for the wide and narrow body aircraft, two prepreg systems have been fully certified.

T300-CFRP fabric- (8H Satin weave 380 g/m²) and tape-prepregs (250 g/m²) are used in combination.

The fabric and tape material were separately certified for both resin systems, because at the time of certification there was an insufficient data base on the mechanical performance of different prepregs.

It is well known that composite materials absorb water during in-service life, due to environmental conditions. The water absorption of composite materials leads to an increase in weight and much more important to a degradation of the mechanical performances, especially at elevated temperatures.

To enable the accurate prediction of composite structures mechanical performance subjected to in-service high moisture environmental conditions, a mechanical testing program was carried out on laminates having an equivalent long term real life moisture content.

From experience it is known that under same environmental conditions, resin systems absorb different amounts of moisture. For this reason, for testing purposes it is more accurate to use different moisture content percentages for different resin systems (Fig. 10).

In order to define an individual in-service moisture content for each resin system, an artificial climate had to be defined which subjected the resin system in a short period of time in the laboratory, to the equivalent effect of a long term real environment exposure. After review of all current information including the evaluation of coupon tests, in-service specimen from spoilers, specimen flying inside a metal fin box and ground exposure of specimen in N.W. Germany, the artificial 'service climate' for environmental testing at the 'Mastersystem' was found to be:

70°C and 70 - 75% relative humidity

FIG. 10 EXPOSURE RATE OF DIFFERENT COMPOSITES

For the two prepreg systems in use for the production of the fin components this laboratory climate lead to a equilibrium moisture pick up of

0.9% for HEXCEL F550

1.1% for FIBREDUX 913C

FIG. 11 TEMPERATURE RELATED STIFFNESS

TEMPERATURE ON GROUND (without operational loads)		
Skin	Tmax = + 90 °C	Tmin = - 40 °C
Stiffener	Tmax = + 90 °C	Tmin = - 40 °C
TEMPERATURE IN FLIGHT (maximum static load possible)		
Skin	Tmax = + 60 °C	Tmin = - 40 °C
Skin	Tmax = + 68 °C (*)	
Stiffener	Tmax = + 70 °C	Tmin = - 50 °C
Stiffener	Tmax = + 70 °C (*)	

(*) Assumption: 30 minutes waiting for take off clearance after taxiing, same fin side facing the sun

FIG. 12 TEMPERATURE SPECTRA OF THE AIRBUS FIN

ted as B-values and moduli of elasticity data as C-values (minimum and maximum average with 95% confidence bound). Both calculations were performed using a minimum of 3 batches each with 6 samples.

Computation of strength values was performed using a method based on MIL-HDBK-17.

8. ANALYSIS AND DESIGN LIMITS

It is well known that detailed investigations of the composite material on coupon specimen basis is not sufficient to prepare the application of composites to complex aircraft structures. For the Airbus fin structures detailed analysis and testing had to be carried out far more intensive and extensive than it would have been carried out for similar metal structures. A factor of two can be quantified for the engineering of the wide body pilot parts. The global structural analysis was performed using the Finite Element Method NASTRAN program. The model included the rear fuselage with suitable boundary conditions to simulate the stiffness and thermal expansion effects.

One of the fundamental physical properties of thermosetting composites is its stability at elevated temperatures. In a wide temperature range of -50°C up to +70°C the cured resins in use show a relatively stable performance. On reaching a temperature above 100°C the resin starts to loose performance very rapidly. The reason for the degradation in performance are brought about by changes in the physical/chemical structure of the molecules. The temperature area, where this rapid loss of performance starts is named the 'glass transition temperature' (TG).

These data were measured by using the pendulum test and dynamic mechanical analysis.

MBS uses the method of 5% stiffness reduction. The resulting temperature value is defined as the 'softening temperature' (TS), (Fig. 11).

For the material selection the softening temperature of laminates in wet condition was defined to be 25°C higher than the max. in-service temperature of the loaded component.

According to the above values the CFRP systems had to agree with a TS / wet higher than + 95°C (Fig. 12).

For the design and fabrication of light-weight CFRP structures, it is important to ascertain the accurate material allowable values, and to continuously control these values. A large number of coupon tests were carried out and pooled to a data base. By using a special statistical method, the material values were calculated from the data base.

The ultimate strength data were calculated as B-values and moduli of elasticity data as C-values (minimum and maximum average with 95% confidence bound).

Fig. 13 FINAL MESH FOR A RIB WEB

Fig. 14 DESIGN CRITERIA

9. FULL SCALE TESTING

For the A310 rudder the demonstration of static strength and fatigue/damage tolerance was performed with separate test specimens, all follow up fin structures were justified by only one specimen covering all static strength and fatigue/damage tolerance aspects. This procedure resulted in good efficiency with respect to time and costs in demonstrating strength for new and aged conditions. Ageing does not only mean moisture pick up but also refers to life/load cycling. Using this approach some risk may arise in the case that the test specimen fails either due to uncontrolled test loading or structural reasons. MBB experienced both incidents but was always able to react in time by replacing the complete test specimen or by repairing the specimen. In each case the ultimate strength after two test lives could be demonstrated before type certification.

At a later stage the resulting strains were compared with the measured strains from full scale testing, and in general were found to be in good agreement. In a few cases the test results led to a revision and refinement of the structural mesh. This was the case in the load introduction areas of the fin root and shear webs of spars and ribs. An example of a final mesh is given with Fig. 13. For the different types of structure as there are sandwich and discrete stiffened panels, fittings and shear webs, the design limits were derived from element and subcomponent tests. The design criteria had to cover stiffness, strength, instability, fatigue and damage tolerance under all applicable environmental conditions. As an example, Fig. 14 shows a criteria used for the fin box panels. For all monolithic panels including the rudders and fin boxes, a design criteria was defined that buckling would not occur below limit loads. This criteria was only important in a few areas, where the minimum skin and web thickness was 1.1 mm. All applied criteria led to a global ultimate strain level well below 3.2‰ which was locally exceeded at the edges of holes especially at fittings.

For the applied design principles and strain level, significant damages can be tolerated possibly having their origin in the production and in-service events. Detail and full scale test specimen were prepared with artificial damages. It was shown that rudder panels could sustain damages greater than 1000 mm² and the fin box panels greater than 2000 mm², up to ultimate loads under worst environmental conditions. Detailed information about the damage tolerance behaviour and according justification is given in [7] and [9].

FIG. 15 FULL SCALE TEST SET UP

FIG. 16 DELAMINATION OF THE RIB 1 CONNECTING ANGLE

FIG. 17 IMPROVED DESIGN

All the full scale testing was carried out within a climate chamber (Fig. 15) so that fatigue and static testing could be run under realistic and worst environmental conditions. This test method represents the most realistic approach. For future developments of wing and fuselage structures this approach may not be feasible or too expensive. In that case realistic enhancement factors on loading must be derived by coupon, element and subcomponent testing covering the strength degradation due to the environment. Summarizing the experience from the full scale testing it can be stated that the re-realized fin structures were not sensitive to fatigue. Damages up to sizes which were just detectable by visual inspection did not propagate during the fatigue loading and the following ultimate test.

There was one exception which has to be mentioned. After accumulation of 37496 test flights the A320 full scale fin test was stopped because of a delamination between the front main fitting and the root rib connection angle (Fig. 16). Transverse reaction loads at the main fitting had overloaded the bonded connection.

The connection was improved by additional bolts similar to that already employed on the A310 fin box structure (Fig. 17). After the repair, the testing was continued and finished successfully. This was the only structural failure experienced during the full scale fatigue testing caused by a local poor design with respect to peeling.

10. MANUFACTURING

The design features of the rudders and the fin boxes led to different manufacturing processes. The very simple sandwich construction of the rudder allows simple tooling and manual fabrication to a much wider extent, than was possible with the more complex fin box. The rudder sandwich panel production is characterized by cutting and lay up procedures of fabric prepregs and NOMEX cores. Prepreg cutting and trimming is subject to mechanisation. The assembly is carried out manually. A higher degree of automation and mechanisation is possible and necessary for the fin boxes [8]. The originally planned automated production centre as outlined in [1] (Fig. 18) has not been fully realized but mechanisation has been applied to almost all production steps, including

FIG. 18 ORIGINALLY PLANNED AUTOMATED PRODUCTION CENTRE

- cutting with the Gerber cutter
- transportation and storage of cutted prepregs
- tape laying of skin panel reinforcements
- transportation of module toolings using a code system
- semi mechanical bandaging of prepregs around the module cores
- positioning of the bandaged modules in the module pallets
- cleaning and reassembling of module cores after curing
- ultrasonic squirter testing

Fig. 19 illustrates the manufacture of the fin box side panels.

The assembly is mainly carried out manually supported by special assembly line tools.

FIG. 19 FIN BOX PANEL MANUFACTURE

It has been experienced that the introduction of automation and mechanisation normally has its basis and starting point in a manual production according to a design that allows automation. The degree of the industrial success is strongly dependent on the investments staked for the right items at the right time.

11. QUALITY

All steps of the production process are under quality control. It is subdivided in incoming and inprocess inspection, component and assembly control. In order to guarantee an acceptable level of quality within an economical production it became necessary to define tolerable deficiencies with respect to porosities, delaminations, resin contents and geometric tolerances. These limits depend on the structural importance and the existing strain levels of the different areas of the fin. Quality control after manufacturing guarantees, that damages or failures beyond those limits will be recognized and subject to a concession. The given limits were justified by analysis and testing.

FIG. 20 ULTRA SONIC SQUIRTER TEST

At the beginning of the research program the quality assurance staff had to learn about the possibilities of finding deficiencies in the composites using different nondestructive inspection hardware. The engineering staff had to learn how to correctly interpret the reading results. Today most of the parts are controlled by ultrasonic techniques. In addition X-ray techniques are employed. Fig. 20 shows a 12 by 3 meter high performance squirter test equipment where 100% of the stiffened panels are ultrasonic tested.

Nondestructive testing is not scheduled for in-service fin structures during normal maintenance. The design aim for the composite structures was not to cause extra maintenance in comparison with metal structures. Justification for this approach was given by the damage tolerance

demonstration in the full scale tests, where small visible failures did not degrade the strength below ultimate load.

At the time of writing this paper, in December 1988, Airbus Industrie had not been informed by any of its customers of in-service problems associated with the composite tail structures.

12. CONCLUSIONS

- Up to Dec. 1988 more than 250 Airbus aircraft are flying with carbon fibre composite fin structures without any reported problems.
- Sandwich and monolithic design have demonstrated good performance
- Resins curing at 125°C are applicable to fin structures
- It was shown that weight savings of 20% against metal structures can be realized by using composite construction without any degradation of safety
- The ultimate strain level below 0.32% was proven not to create any structural fatigue failures nor propagation of artificial defects applied to the test specimens.
- From the outset of all structural testing, artificial structural damages were introduced, so as to cover scatter due to variation in manufacturing quality and to justify an cost effective inspection and maintenance program.

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2. Manufacture

